

IODINATION OF SOME COUMARIN DERIVATIVES*

BY S. S. LELE, M. G. PATEL AND SURESH SETHNA

The iodination of 7-hydroxycoumarin and substituted 5- and 7-hydroxycoumarins, and their methyl ethers with substituents, such as, carboxyl, carbomethoxyl and nitro groups, has been studied using different iodinating agents.

The work on the iodination of coumarin derivatives has been extended; the iodination of several 7- and 5-hydroxycoumarin derivatives has been studied, using (a) iodine monochloride, (b) iodine and iodic acid ($5RH + 4I + HIO_3 \longrightarrow 5RI + 3H_2O$), and (c) iodine and ammonia as iodinating agents.

7-Hydroxycoumarin on iodination, by the three methods, with theoretical amounts of the iodinating agents furnished in each case the 8-iodo derivative. Its methyl ether neither gave a coumarilic acid derivative on boiling with alkali nor did it undergo the Elbs persulphate oxidation, indicating that the iodine had not entered either the 3- or the 6-position (cf. Dalvi, Desai and Sethna, *this Journal*, 1953, 30, 610). With two moles of iodine in presence of ammonia the 6:8-diiodo compound was obtained. Its methyl ether remained unchanged on boiling with alkali. The 3:6:8-triiodo derivative was obtained on iodination with double the theoretical amounts of iodine and iodic acid, and with excess of the other two iodinating agents. Its methyl ether furnished a diiodocoumarilic acid derivative on boiling with alkali.

7-Methoxycoumarin gave with one mole of iodine monochloride the 3-iodo derivative. With alkali it afforded the known 6-methoxycoumarilic acid (Seshadri and Varadrajana, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 39). The other two methods did not yield any iodo product. With four moles of iodine monochloride it gave the 3:6-diiodo derivative. Its methyl ether furnished a monoiodocoumarilic acid. Further, it was different from the 3:8-diiodo derivative, synthesised by iodinating the 7-methoxy-8-iodocoumarin with iodine monochloride, and which gave an isomeric monoiodocoumarilic acid.

The iodination of 7-hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid, 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid, and its methyl ester and methyl 5-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylate with theoretical amounts of the iodinating agents gave the corresponding 8-iodo derivatives by the three methods. The methyl ethers of the iodo-coumarin esters on hydrolysis afforded only the corresponding coumarin carboxylic acids. In no case was a coumarilic acid derivative formed. No further iodination of the above coumarins could be achieved by any of the three methods except in the case of 7-hydroxycoumarin-6-carboxylic acid, which on iodination with double the quantities of iodine and iodic acid gave the 3:8-diiodo derivative, the methoxy derivative of which furnished a monoiodocoumarilic acid.

* Previous paper: S. S. Lele and Suresh Sethna, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, 23, 1731.

On iodination with one mole of iodine monochloride, methyl 7-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylate and its 4-methyl analogue gave the 3-iodo derivatives, which were degraded to the corresponding coumarilic acid derivatives with alkali. The methoxy esters could not be iodinated by the other two methods. Methyl-5-methoxycoumarin-6-carboxylate and its 4-methyl analogue gave monoiodo derivatives, which could not be degraded to the corresponding coumarilic acid derivatives and were therefore assigned the 8-iodo structures. For the same reason the product obtained on the iodination of 7-hydroxy-6-nitro-4-methylcoumarin with iodine and iodic acid was assigned the 8-iodo structure. This nitrocoumarin could not be iodinated by the other two methods, and further iodination with iodine and iodic acid could not be achieved.

In the iodination of 7-hydroxy-4-methylcoumarin-8-carboxylic acid with iodine and ammonia, the carboxyl group was eliminated and the known 7-hydroxy-8-iodo-4-methylcoumarin was obtained.

7-Hydroxycoumarin-4-acetic acid yielded the 8-iodo derivative on iodination by all the three methods. Methyl ether of the ester of this iodocoumarin on alkaline hydrolysis lost the carbomethoxy group and gave the known 7-methoxy-8-iodo-4-methylcoumarin. On iodination with two moles of iodine in presence of ammonia, the 6:8-diiodo derivative was obtained. During methylation of this compound decarboxylation occurred, and the known 7-methoxy-6:8-diiodo-4-methylcoumarin was obtained. No triiodo derivative was obtained with excess of iodine and ammonia, but with double the quantities of iodine and iodic acid, the 3:6:8-triiodo derivative was obtained. During methylation it underwent decarboxylation and provided the known 7-methoxy-3:6:8-triiodo-4-methylcoumarin.

EXPERIMENTAL

General Iodination Procedures

(a) *With Iodine Monochloride.*—To the coumarin derivative (0.01M), dissolved in minimum quantity of glacial acetic acid, HCl (d 1.1, 15 c.c.) was added. The mixture was added to the requisite amount of iodine monochloride and kept for 24 hours at 50°. The iodo derivative, which separated from the solution as such or on dilution with water, was crystallised from acetic acid. In the case of methoxycoumarin derivatives the iodination products were not readily obtained if hydrochloric acid was used, and hence it was dispensed with.

(b) *With Iodine and Iodic Acid.*—The coumarin derivative (0.01M) was dissolved in minimum quantity of warm ethanol and the requisite amount of iodine was added. To the warm dark coloured solution obtained the required amount of iodic acid, dissolved in water, was added with stirring. The reaction mixture was stirred for 2 hours and the iodo derivative, which separated as such or on dilution with water, was crystallised from acetic acid.

(c) *With Iodine and Ammonia.*—To the coumarin derivative (0.01M), dissolved in dilute ammonia, a solution of iodine in potassium iodide in required quantity was added with stirring at room temperature during 1/2 hour. The reaction mixture was then poured into excess of dilute ice-cold sulphuric acid. The precipitated iodo derivative was crystallised from acetic acid.

Products obtained on iodination by the three methods are recorded in Table I.

Preparation of Methyl Ethers.—The iodo derivatives were methylated by refluxing their acetone solutions with dimethyl sulphate in presence of anhydrous potassium carbonate (Table II).

Hydrolysis of Methoxyiodocoumarins.—The methoxyiodocoumarins were hydrolysed by boiling with 10% ethanolic KOH for 2 hours (Table III).

TABLE I
Products obtained on iodination.

No.	Coumarin.	Method.	Product.	*M.P.	% Yield.	Formula.	% Iodine Found.	% Iodine Calc.
1.	7-Hydroxy-	a, b, c, c	8-Iodo 6:8-Diiodo	228-32° 232°	10,49,80 9	C ₉ H ₆ O ₃ I C ₉ H ₄ O ₃ I ₂	44.1 61.7	44.1 61.3
		a, b, c.	3:6:8-Triiodo	235°	56	C ₉ H ₂ O ₃ I ₃	70.5	70.6
2.	7-Methoxy-	a	3-Iodo	155-56°	17	C ₁₀ H ₈ O ₃ I	42.3	42.4
		a	3:6-Diiodo	246-47°	47	C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₃ I ₂	59.4	59.3
3.	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-	a	3:8-Diiodo	238°	46	C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₃ I ₂	59.5	59.3
4.	7-Hydroxy-6-carboxy-	a, b, c, b	8-Iodo 3:8-Diiodo	258-60° 272°	45, 54, 9 11	C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₄ I C ₁₀ H ₄ O ₄ I ₂ · 2H ₂ O†	38.4 50.8	38.3 51.4
5.	7-Methoxy-6-carbomethoxy-	a	3-Iodo	245-46°	72	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₃ I	35.2	35.3
6.	7-Hydroxy-4-acetic acid	a, b, c, c	8-Iodo 6:8-Diiodo	227-28° 235-36°	72, 58, 72 74	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₄ I C ₁₁ H ₆ O ₄ I ₂ · H ₂ O**	36.6 51.8	36.7 51.8
		b	3:6:8-Triiodo	238-40°	67	C ₁₁ H ₄ O ₄ I ₃	64.2	63.7
7.	5-Methoxy-6-carbomethoxy	a	8-Iodo	157-58°	31	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ I	34.7	35.3
8.	7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-carboxy-	c	8-Iodo	273°	66	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₃ I	36.7	36.7
9.	7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-carbomethoxy-	a, b, c.	8-Iodo	285°	13, 53, 76	C ₁₂ H ₈ O ₃ I	36.0	35.3
10.	7-Methoxy-4-methyl-6-carbomethoxy-	a	3-Iodo	234°	66	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ I	34.1	33.9
11.	7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-8-carboxy-	c	7-Hydroxy-8-iodo-4-methylcoumarin	..	..	..	..	..
12.	5-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-carbomethoxy-	a, b.	8-Iodo	254°	21, 48	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ I	35.4	35.3
13.	5-Methoxy-4-methyl-6-carbomethoxy-	a	8-Iodo	154°	54	C ₁₂ H ₁₁ O ₃ I	34.2	33.9
14.	* 7-Hydroxy-4-methyl-6-nitro-	b	8-Iodo	273°	62	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₃ NI	36.1	36.6

* All the melting points are uncorrected. Hydroxyiodo derivatives start decomposing 20-30° below their melting points and melt finally at the mentioned temperatures.

† Analysis after drying at 110° in vacuum. Found: I, 53.0%. C₁₀H₆O₄ · H₂O requires I, 53.3%.

‡ The product decomposes on drying at 110° in vacuum.

TABLE II
Methyl ethers of the hydroxyiodocoumarins*

No.	Coumarin.	M.P.	Formula.	%Carbon.		%Hydrogen.		%Iodine.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
1	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-	158°	$C_{10}H_7O_2I$	40.1	40.0	2.5	2.3	41.9	42.4
2	7-Methoxy-6,8-diiodo-	168-70°	$C_{10}H_5O_2I_2$	27.6	28.0	1.5	1.4	59.0	59.3
3	7-Methoxy-3,6,8-triiodo-	208-10°	$C_{10}H_3O_2I_3$	21.9	21.7	1.2	0.9	68.2	68.8
4	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-6-carbomethoxy-	162°	$C_{12}H_9O_4I$	39.6	40.0	2.8	2.5	35.6	35.3
5	7-Methoxy-3,8-diiodo-6-carbomethoxy-	205-206°	$C_{12}H_7O_4I_2$	29.5	29.6	2.1	1.6	52.3	52.3
6	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-4-carbomethoxymethyl-	140-42°	$C_{12}H_{11}O_4I$	42.2	41.7	3.3	2.9	34.1	33.9
7	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-4-methyl-6-carbomethoxy-	223°	$C_{12}H_{11}O_4I$	41.6	41.7	2.9	2.9	33.9	33.9
8	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-4-methyl-6-nitro-	242°	$C_{11}H_9O_4NI$	36.2	36.6	2.1	2.2	34.8	35.2

* Mentioned in Table I.

TABLE III
Hydrolysis products of the methoxyiodocoumarins.

No.	Coumarin.	Product.	M.P.	Formula.	% Carbon. Found.	% Carbon. Calc.	% Hydrogen. Found.	% Hydrogen. Calc.	% Iodine. Found.	% Iodine. Calc.
1.	7-Methoxy-3,6-diiodo-	6-Methoxy-5-iodo-coumarilic acid	258°	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₄ I	37.5	37.7	2.2	2.2	39.8	39.9
2.	7-Methoxy-3,8-diiodo-	6-Methoxy-7-iodo-coumarilic acid	280°	C ₁₀ H ₇ O ₄ I	37.5	37.7	2.6	2.2	40.4	39.9
3.	7-Methoxy-3,6,8-triiodo-	6-Methoxy-5,7-diodocoumarilic acid	240°	C ₁₀ H ₆ O ₄ I ₂	27.4	27.0	1.8	1.4	57.2	57.2
4.	7-Methoxy-3-iodo-6-carbomethoxy-	6-Methoxy-5-carboxycoumarilic acid	285°	C ₁₁ H ₈ O ₄	56.2	55.9	3.4	3.4	..	..
5.	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-6-carbomethoxy-	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-coumarin-6-carboxylic acid	236°	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₄ I	38.5	38.2	2.3	2.0	36.8	36.7
6.	5-Methoxy-8-iodo-6-carbomethoxy-	5-Methoxy-8-iodo-coumarin-6-carboxylic acid	238°	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₄ I	38.0	38.2	2.4	2.0	37.0	36.7
7.	7-Methoxy-3,8-diiodo-6-carbomethoxy-	6-Methoxy-7-iodo-5-carboxycoumarilic acid	272°	C ₁₁ H ₇ O ₄ I	37.0	36.5	2.2	1.9	34.7	35.1
8.	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-4-carbomethoxymethyl-	*7-Methoxy-8-iodo-4-methylcoumarin	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
9.	7-Methoxy-3-iodo-4-methyl-6-carbomethoxy-	**6-Methoxy-5-carboxy-3-methylcoumarilic acid	..	..	..	..	..	..	..	..
10.	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-4-methyl-6-carbomethoxy-	7-Methoxy-8-iodo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid	237°	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₄ I	39.8	40.0	2.3	2.5	35.2	35.3
11.	5-Methoxy-8-iodo-4-methyl-6-carbomethoxy-	5-Methoxy-8-iodo-4-methylcoumarin-6-carboxylic acid	245°	C ₁₂ H ₉ O ₄ I	39.6	40.0	2.3	2.5	35.6	35.3

* Lajla and Sethna (*loc. cit.*)

** Dalvi and Sethna, this *Journal*, 1949, 28, 359, 467.

6-Hydroxy-7-methoxy-8-iodocoumarin.—7-Methoxy-8-iodocoumarin (3.02 g.) was dissolved in 10% NaOH solution (80 c.c.) by warming on a steam bath. It was then oxidised with potassium persulphate (2.5 g. in 120 c.c. water) according to the procedure described by Parikh and Sethna (this *Journal*, 1950, **27**, 369). The product obtained was crystallised from dilute ethanol in needles, m.p. 217°. (Found: C, 37.7; H, 2.5; I, 39.9. $C_{10}H_7O_4I$ requires C, 37.7; H, 2.2; I, 39.9%).

One of the authors (M.G.P.) thanks the Government of India for the award of a research scholarship.

ORGANIC CHEMISTRY LABORATORIES,
MAHARAJA SAYAJIRAO UNIVERSITY OF BARODA,
BARODA.

Received September 9, 1960.